

A Review On The Factors Which Improve Employees' Productivity And Enhance Their Performance In An Organization

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Abstract- The skilled and educated workforce plays a vital role in any organization's growth, development, and success and hence it also depends on the employee's performance. Every year organizations exclusively allocate a huge amount of money for improving the abilities of employees for better performance and satisfactory results. Therefore, human resources are the most valuable assets of today's organization and the purpose of the organization lies in the optimum utilization of its employees at all levels. The objective of this study is to increase employee productivity and effective use of existing resources such as raw material, machinery equipment, technology, capital, and human resources by means of existing literature. In this study, four critical success factors of employee productivity have been identified namely workforce empowerment, time management, workplace environment, and teamwork. Employee productivity not only affects the performance of employees, however, also helps to cope with stress, conflict, and pressure more efficiently. It also helps them to maintain a healthy work-life balance and keeps them motivated. Indeed, good performance of employees is not only beneficial for the organization, actually, in the long time, it would also be more effective for society and leads to progress of the community as a whole. The finding of this study exposes that there is a positive relationship between employee productivity and employee performance because employee productivity leads to the growth and development of the overall organization. Hence, this study is an attempt to give insight into the key parameters of the corporate world which may create more productive and performance-oriented employees and further bring success to the organization as compared to its competitors.

Keywords- Time Management, Workforce, Environment: Productivity, Performance, Employee Empowerment, Teamwork.

I. Introduction

Human resource is the most valuable and the most important factor in the development of any country. Studies show that countries that have high Net National Product (NNP) usually have more trained and educated human resources. Productivity is the gem of the organization which guarantees the stability and survival of any organization. "Employee productivity is an assessment of the efficiency of a worker or group of workers. In actual terms, productivity is a component that directly affects the company's profits" (Hanaysh, 2016). Therefore, the objective of every firm is to recruit employees who are effective for the company in the present as well as the future. Hence, the organization's goal is to enable the workforce to contribute effectively and productively to its overall growth. Cato & Gordon (2009) stated that the success of every organization depends on its employee's productivity. Hence, productivity

becomes vital for the survival of every organization. Employee productivity is the chief instrument to enhance the organization's performance and increase the quality of goods/services it offers without incurring extra costs. With skilled and educated employees, the quality of products will increase. This increase in quality will in turn lead to an increase in the number of products sold as well as company profits (Salam, How, & Faisae, 2012). Indeed, the management's main mission in every organization is the effective use of various resources in the company such as human resources, raw materials, technology, asset, energy, and information. In actual terms, effective use of these resources depends on the employees' performance and productivity. Thus, productivity means utilizing the available resources in a scientific manner to reduce production costs, expand the market, increase quality as well the company's profits. In the words of Nda & Fard (2013), "The success of the organization is . . . dependent on its knowledgeable, skilled as well as experienced workforce, employee's performance, and its employee's productivity".

Furthermore, employee productivity and performance play a crucial role in the prosperity of every organization. Employee performance means how the workforce fulfills its job duties and the executive its required tasks in the organization. So, a performing employee is extremely valuable to a company. This article will explore the use of various ways and previously existing methods which can increase the ability and productivity of the employees in the organization. Better productivity and employee performance in the organization empower the company. Hameed & Waheed (2011) opine that "Employee Performance means employee productivity and output as a result of employee development. Employee performance will ultimately affect organizational effectiveness". (Ganta, 2014) Development and progress of the organization are dependent on employee performance and productivity. Therefore, organizations invest a huge amount of money every year in employee development.

II. Literature Review

The Impact of Employee Empowerment on Productivity

Employees empowerment has been defined by many scholars with various meanings. (Hieu, 2020) "Empowerment fosters employees' creativity, quality of work-life, a spirit of teamwork, and organizational effectiveness"(20-25).empowering makes an employee more active and increases their abilities in a scientific way for doing their job duties, empowerment, and productivity in the company which has a direct effect and they play a vital role in the growth of the organization. Nwachukwa (2017) stated that empowerment increases employee trust, loyalty, commitment, and productivity within the organization, empowerment can enhance the responsibilities as well as the motivation of employees in their routine work. Therefore, empowerment is one of the most crucial elements for increasing employee productivity as well as for better doing their task in the organization. The objectives of every organization are the effective use of available sources, especially their employee within the firm. (Aghimien & Aigbavboa, 2017) stated, the main objective of every organization is to achieve the organization's goals and to develop their employee's skills so developed employees

may have a direct impact on employee productivity and employee performance within the organization and may lead to an increase in the company profits.

The impact of the work environment on employee productivity

A favorable environment is having a major role in boosting employee productivity and improving organizational performance. Furthermore, a suitable workplace leads to the reduction of absenteeism and encourages the workforce to be on time and they can feel more comfortable conducting their duties better. In addition, most of the time the employees in a favorable environment can implement their ideas for the development and progress of the organization. Hafeez, Hafeez, Mansoor, & Cheema(2017), have expressed that the work atmosphere significantly impacts the performances of the employees, and the employees can use their skills, competencies, and knowledge to execute their tasks efficiently in the organization. therefore, we can say that some elements in the environment have negative and some have positive effects on the organization. furthermore, in developing countries, the workplace environment has the chief role in developing employee performance and productivity because most of the industries are located within the cities and laborers are facing problems such as noise pollution, traffic problems, and insufficient areas for producing products, so, these have negative effects on employees performance. Moreover, in most of the industries in developing countries' environments in the suburbs, the workforce can perform their work in a quiet environment and they may keep themselves free from evolving risks, such as stressful working conditions (Cottini & Ghinetti, 2012). So, the impact of the work environment is really important and hence, employers should create a suitable work environment for the employees where the workforce might be kept away from the work stress and they can use all their skills, and abilities, for prospering and developing the organization.

The impact of time management on employees' productivity

Time management means cleverly working to increase effectiveness, efficiency, and productivity at a specific time." Effective time management not only affects the productivity of your employees but also helps to cope with stress, conflicts, and pressure more efficiently" (Daniel & Santeli, 2020, pp. 72-82).therefore, one of the most effective tools to enhance the productivity of the workforce is time management training. in time management training, employees are ready with the specific planning and management system that assist employees to have more control over their time for better performance. therefore, effective utilization of time, employees, and raw materials to enhance employee productivity, reduce costs, and increase profit is the objective of every organization. Onyepuemu (2017) stated, that achieving individual and organizational goals is dependent on the limited amount of time that is determined. So, the influence of time management is very important for enhancing employee productivity within a specified time. With proper planning and appropriate guidance, employee productivity and performance will increase. Time management is the process of organizing and planning how much time employees spend on particular activities and how employee manages their tasks at a specific time. So, we can say, time management is having a positive linkage with the overall growth of the organization.

The main purpose of any organization is that at least they must have optimum usage of time to increase employee productivity, and hence the organization's revenues.

The impact of teamwork on employee productivity

Teamwork is the collaborative effort of a group to acquire common goals or a group of people to work together for achieving the particular objective of the organization or to complete tasks most effectively and efficiently. Ueno (2018) stated that every teamwork aims to improve employee collaboration and productivity in the organization, and teamwork causes employees to share information and knowledge along with their teammates to increase the quality of goods and services. Nowadays, many organizations are making efforts to create a favorable environment for the employees to work simultaneously for learning from each other's during tasks in the organization because working together is the base for employees to know their weaknesses, work upon increasing their strengths, and lower the weaknesses. (Oteshova, Niyazbayeva, Prodanova, Sabirova, & Zayed, 2021) the success and failure of every organization depend on its own employees' performance like how they perform their jobs duties, and how much they are in harmony at their tasks with each other. Therefore, teamwork focuses on the employees to show their hidden talent and skills so as to solve their problems more effectively and efficiently altogether. In addition, the impact of teamwork on employee productivity is really important for the better result of the organization. In modern businesses, all companies focus on providing a favorable workplace for employees to share their ideas and obtain the best result.

Also, many researchers have argued upon many factors and methods that influence employee productivity and help in improving the company output by making the best use of its input.

There are two major factors that affect employee productivity and performance:

Internal factors and external factors.

The above factors have been argued by (Anwar & Abdullah, 2021). Mahamid, Al-Ghonamy, & Aichouni (2013), (Goel, Agrewal, & Sharma, 2017) (Kohil, 2008), and (Aguinis, 2014), have a really significant influence on employee productivity and performance in the purpose of achieving the organization's objectives. If any organization has to survive the competition in the market should consider the available prospects that have more influence as well as better effects on the organization's efficiency because every environment and arising opportunities have its own characteristics for producing the goods and services.

III. Internal factors:

Skilled human resources:

Human resources are one of the imperative units of the organization, so the success and failure of the organization are dependent on their performance. Every organization are trying to improve their employee’s skills for better results which leads to a profitable unit. The impact of skilled employees is not only for the betterment of the company but also provides the society by using the resources effectively and efficiently.

Technology:

Technology is an instrument that is used to produce and build better products. Better products are that which has produced at the lowest cost and have the best performance. Modern economic technology has really influenced production commodities and also employee productivity. Nowadays most organizations use modernist technology for better efficiency as well as for better employee performance in the organization.

Financial:

Financial management concepts of planning, organizing, staffing, and directing the organization’s financial activities for the purpose of achieving the best performance. The survival of any organization is dependent on its financial source. Every year most organizations exclusively use huge amounts of money on training and developing employees for more effectiveness.

Machinery and Equipment:

Modernist machinery and equipment cause has a foster effect on producing the product in the shortest time with good quality. Machinery and equipment have a direct cause of effect on producing the goods and services and make it much stress-free work for employees to accomplish their job duties in the best manner as well as with low cost. Machinery and equipment make more activities for employees for better results and it saves time.

Workplace Environment:

It is true workplace has more effect on employee productivity than the other organizational elements in some favorable environments employees can conduct their job duties well mannered. A favorable workplace environment increases the efficiency of workers and also decreases the turnover of the employees in the organization.

Management:

This is because management determines how employees should perform their tasks and which roles and regulations should they follow, during their work in the organization. Management is the process of designing and maintaining an environment in which individuals, working together in groups, efficiently accomplish selected goals.

2- External Factors:

External factors are those factors that have directly and indirectly impacted employee productivity such as government rules and regulations, natural resources, and infrastructure.

Government rules.

there are many factors that have a direct and indirect influence on producing the products, the government rules, and the police also govern any organization, by following that rules which government determines they should continue their activities. Squire & Wilder (2010) proposed “that rules are the function altering contingencies-specifying stimuli” (57-69). Implementation, of rules and regulations in the organization and following the globalization standards, will lead to the growth and development of the company as well as increase employee productivity and enhance their performance [. (Agnew, 1998). In reality, the government guidelines in the industries area cause of increasing the quality of commodities as well as enhance the people situation life.

Infrastructure:

One of the basic concepts in the Marxism school is infrastructure and superstructure, they believed that the power of a country depended on its infrastructure. according to Marxism, school infrastructure is a very important key for cultivation and product as well as for producing goods and services. In very developing countries governments allocate especially areas for factories in order better employee performance. because in the crowed area employees can't focus on their work.

Natural resource:

Overall, natural resources are resources that exist without any action of humankind, natural resource is a part of humankind. indeed, human life is affiliated with natural resources it is very difficult to imagine life without them. Natural resources include atmospheres, sunlight, land, water, all minerals along with all vegetation, and animal life. Roles of land, iron, coal and other factors also are very important in producing goods/services. Most of the organizations try to use raw materials of high quality. for this reason, we can say production resources are the primary step for counties of organization activities.

summary of productivity

Asian Productivity Organization	In development approaches to human resource management, clearly about the importance and position of the human factors in the organization is considered as important.
Iranian National Productivity organization	One of the most effective factors in improving the performance of the employees of the organization is the growth of feeling of ability among the employees.
Oxford dictionary	According to the Oxford dictionary, (productivity) means getting power, licensing, ability, and feeling freedom for conducting the tasks in the organization.
Organization for European Economic Co-operation	Productivity is one of the factors that ensure the durability and survival of organizations in the current world.
Wikipedia	Productivity is one of the most important factors of production
Japan Productivity Center	Productivity is to maximize the use of resources, human resources and Facilitates the scientific way, reduces production costs, expands markets, increases employment, and effort to increase real wages and improve the living level.
Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development	productivity is a culture and its purpose of cleverly conducting activities and achieving a better life

International Labour Organization	Productivity means effective exploitation and increase desirability in all dimensions of the organization
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The benefits of improving organizational productivity

Improvement and promotion of organizational efficiency require effort and comprehensive planning by top people in the organization such as the president, vice president, department head, supervisors, and employees but its results are really noticeable,

1. Increased profits and income
2. Reduce costs
3. speed of employee action
4. Accuracy of the staff
5. Increase salary and wages.
6. public education of the employee.
7. employee's job security.
8. create better competition.
9. creating an attractive work environment.
10. employee's, job satisfaction
11. doing the right things
12. increase the quality of work-life
13. increase employee welfare
14. Generates revenues

IV. DISCUSSIONS & CONCLUSION

regarding this research considers how to improve employee productivity and the ways to enhance their performance in the organization. The approach which is used for this research is annotated bibliography, in this article many resources used such as journals, websites, news, reports, books, and magazine articles which were published by authentic authors. Also described and analyzed external and internal factors that have direct and indirect impacts on employee productivity which was argued by three scientists Mahamid, Al-Ghonamy, & Aichouni. Their findings were interpreted and analyzed independently, and then presented clearly and accurately. To this research, the funded result shows the closest impact relationship between employee productivity and their performance in the organization, in order to increase the profits and income of the organization and to conduct their job duties in the best method. Further, on the literature review, described four elements that have more effective and play a vital role in all organizations such as workplace environment, time management, empowerment, and teamwork these factors are very important for every organization and should have more

consideration to these elements for better results and the best performance of their employees.

Organizations need human resources who can work professionally and excellently and organizations have to provide facilities to their employee to increase their performance for further efficiency and productivity. In the modern and advanced world, competition becomes more and more challenging than in the past any organization going to cover the markets with their commodities. Therefore, producing goods and services with high quality depends on the employee's performance and productivity and how they perform their tasks in the organization. So, employee productivity and their performance determine the organization's survival as well as productivity and excellent performance of employees in the organization cause reducing cost, create better competition, increase the quality of goods, speed employee action, and enhance employee accuracy. these days any organization besides other factors in the organization also has more attention to growing the workforce skills, abilities, and capability. For more efficiency in the organization.

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